

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

PROJECT SYNTHESIS

Deliverable 1.4

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PROJECT SYNTHESIS

The CLEVER Project has run for three years, during a time of major global changes. In this period, the European Union created and approved the Regulation on Deforestation-free products (EUDR), which is now close to implementation. This new regulation will affect many producer countries, including our case studies Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon. As a result, it quickly became one of the main topics studied by the project, together with other forms of market governance and research on biodiversity and modeling.

This synthesis report brings together the project's main findings. It shares the new knowledge created toward biodiversity conservation, and outlines policy recommendations. The overall goal of the project was to find new leverage points for sustainable transformation using a holistic approach to measure biodiversity and the wider impacts of trade in non-food biomass value chains.

To achieve this, the project first looked at gaps across different scientific fields (D2.1) where more research could guide future action for sustainability. Three key areas were identified: (i) measuring **trade impacts on biodiversity**, linking how trade land-use changes affect species and ecosystems; (ii) measuring the effectiveness and determinants of **value chain governance initiatives**, with attention to regional drivers and risks of policy leakage; (iii) using **scenario modeling** to develop actionable scenarios and counterfactuals.

The following sections of this report present the main results from the projects' effort in fulfilling these research gaps, discuss their implications for policy and practice, and suggest ways forward to strengthen global efforts toward biodiversity-friendly value chains.

i) Links between biomass trade and biodiversity

CLEVER research has advanced the understanding of where and why trade in selected biomass supply chain threatens biodiversity. This topic was the focus of WP2, where we combined biodiversity modelling, spatial analysis, and integrated assessment approaches in order to reveal global and regional patterns of biodiversity risks associated with trade.

CLEVER's biodiversity research (D2.2 & D2.3) first identified regions of high conservation priority and areas experiencing significant biodiversity declines. This was supported by improvements in species richness modelling, which incorporated additional databases and allowed for more robust estimates of the impacts of land use and land-use intensity on species richness, endemism, and species composition (D2.4; [Zenodo link](#)).

Several biodiversity indicators and characterization factors (CFs) were produced and made openly available ([Zenodo dataset](#)). They were used to connect biodiversity outcomes with agricultural supply chains in subsequent life-cycle analyses and integrated assessment models in WP6-7. For instance, D6.3 integrated the CFs into the GLOBIOM model to project long-term land-use change (LUC) and biodiversity impacts from agricultural and forestry activities under the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) (Figure 1). The analysis highlighted that, at the global level, pressure on land is the dominant driver of impacts on terrestrial ecosystems, while water stress is more critical for aquatic ecosystems, showing how trade-related drivers influence biodiversity at different ecosystem levels.

Figure 1. In D6.3, we compared the biodiversity impacts due to land occupation in South America and Africa calculated with LC-IMPACT and using the CFs produced in D2.4

Similarly, deliverable D2.5 showed that trade impacts are most strongly associated with land-use change, compared to other environmental factors. However, the analysis also revealed important regional differences. For example, biodiversity in Indonesia and Papua New Guinea could benefit the most from trade-specific policies, whereas in Australia, Sudan, and Niger, climate and fire-specific measures may take precedence. In regions such as Brazil, Angola, and Mozambique, an integrated approach is needed where trade-related policies are aligned with climate and fire-prevention strategies.

In this same deliverable, researchers took a closer look at Brazil to illustrate the importance of land tenure systems in shaping biodiversity outcomes under trade pressure. A spatial overlay analysis revealed that private lands contain higher biodiversity (richness and endemism) per property-km² than rural settlements, protected areas, or indigenous lands (Figure 2). This finding is particularly relevant because private lands are the most exposed to trade-driven market pressures, making them especially vulnerable to biodiversity loss. As a result, it is important to assess the potential of policies that target trade-driven deforestation and biodiversity loss, like the EU Regulation on deforestation-free products (EUDR), to change the behavior of actors that can leverage more sustainable land-use decisions.

Figure 2. Findings from D2.5 connect the different tenure categories in Brazil (A) with their biodiversity indicators and their distribution (species richness (B & D), and endemism (C & E)).

Yet, CLEVER research also shows that policy effectiveness depends on locally heterogeneous incentive structures. In regions with already high levels of conservation on private lands, lasting incentives are required to maintain biodiversity protection. In other regions, such as the Amazon, stronger incentives for legal compliance and restoration are critical to reversing ongoing biodiversity losses.

Taken together, these results demonstrate how CLEVER's trade-specific biodiversity analyses provide insights for policy design and governance. By linking global modelling (D6.3), biodiversity data (D2.2–D2.5), and regional case studies, the project suggests that well-designed trade-related policies can achieve higher conservation impacts at lower costs. Furthermore, CLEVER highlights that such approaches can be integrated into broader research agendas and international governance strategies, making a direct contribution to biodiversity conservation in the context of global biomass trade.

ii) Effectiveness and determinants of value chain governance initiatives

Research from WP3-5 has shown that policy and value chain governance initiatives can reduce biodiversity loss linked to biomass trade, but their effectiveness is highly context-dependent and mediated by multiple factors. Analyses combined empirical data, econometric modelling, mapping of policies and governance regimes, and case studies to examine how different interventions influence deforestation, biodiversity outcomes, and market dynamics.

Firstly, WP3 created a database (D3.1) to estimate trader stickiness (i.e., the tendency of traders to maintain long-term sourcing relationships) and trade substitution elasticities for selected products. This database included proxies for biomass trade, production, demand, and biodiversity, to be used to quantify the impacts through ex-post econometric assessments. The datasets were created around themes, such as international trade networks, biodiversity indicators, aquaculture expansion and trade, land tenure, supply chain governance, and land supply elasticities.

The econometric analyses (D3.3) confirmed that in tropical countries with high soy, cattle, and palm oil production—such as Paraguay, Argentina, Indonesia, and Brazil— the majority of biodiversity loss is driven by commodity expansion rather than other factors (Figure 3). Since much of this production is exported, international trade emerges as a critical driver of biodiversity loss, underscoring the need for effective governance along value chains.

Figure 3. Terrestrial biodiversity loss across the tropics by country calculated in D3.3

The Amazon Soy Moratorium, a non-public multi-stakeholder governance initiative, was designed to address commodity trade driven deforestation. We found that while it is possible to achieve reductions in deforestation alongside improvements in certain biodiversity dimensions, impacts vary substantially across biodiversity metrics. The Amazon Soy Moratorium successfully reduced deforestation and increased species richness and endemism, but it had no effect on phylogenetic diversity.

CLEVER also revealed the importance of value chain dynamics. Sticky soy traders were identified as a mechanism amplifying the Moratorium’s effectiveness, accounting for about a quarter of the observed reductions in deforestation. This finding has direct implications for mandatory due-diligence regulations, such as the EUDR. It suggests that governance effectiveness depends on how key actors respond to and transmit policy incentives across the value chain. However, the willingness of traders to expand conservation commitments to regions not covered by specific regulations remains uncertain.

The project also examined how demand-side preferences in importing countries shape deforestation dynamics. In Brazil, increased EU demand for soy was associated with reduced local deforestation and a shift from forest-to-soy conversion towards pasture-to-soy conversion—an intensification pathway. By contrast, increased Chinese demand was linked to higher deforestation and greater forest-to-soy conversion — an extensification pathway. These results show that international trade can either mitigate or exacerbate biodiversity risks depending on demand-side environmental preferences, but also that reductions in forest loss do not necessarily translate into proportional biodiversity benefits.

In addition, the research findings caution against overreliance on single value chain interventions. While the EU has leveraged its market power to promote deforestation-free supply chains, other major importers (e.g., China) have not. This creates risks of leakage: as long as only a fraction of global demand is regulated, deforestation risks may shift to less scrutinized markets. Moreover, importing regions may selectively source from low-deforestation areas without reducing overall deforestation. Hence, governance effectiveness depends on broad market coverage and international coordination.

Beyond individual supply chain interventions, CLEVER investigated the broader regimes of policies and governance mechanisms shaping biomass trade and biodiversity outcomes. Stakeholder engagement activities (D8.1, D8.5; MS10) mapped leverage points for change in timber, soy, and fishmeal/oil supply chains, while WP4 provided a systematic mapping and classification of international, transnational, and national governance mechanisms (D4.1). This mapping revealed major knowledge gaps regarding (in)coherence between instruments and the need for more research on how to design smart policy mixes.

Zooming in, CLEVER analyzed the theories of change embedded in a selection of international, EU, and national policies and governance mechanisms (D4.2). This revealed that instruments rely on a combination of legally binding and non-binding logics rules, markets, discourses, information, and that their effectiveness depends on designed synergies across these logics.

To assess coherence in practice, D4.3 compared the European Union Regulation on Deforestation-free Products (EUDR) with key policies in producer countries (Brazil, Cameroon, Gabon) and hybrid governance mechanisms (Amazon Soy Moratorium, Cameroon's FLEGT-VPA, Gabon's Mandatory FSC certification). Results showed that while the EUDR is coherent with overarching forest-protection goals and aligned with some enforcement tools, there are also significant incoherences in the form of cooptation and competition over regulatory standards and implementation. These tensions highlight that the EUDR may affect producer-country governance more subtly than expected, potentially undermining existing strategies or creating new frictions. The study underscores that the effectiveness of transnational trade regulations depends on how they interact with existing governance arrangements.

WP 5 complemented these design-oriented analyses by exploring business responses to the EUDR. Value chain analyses (D5.1) showed that compliance is primarily a commercial decision, driven by economic and regulatory logics. EU-based businesses prioritize avoiding penalties, while non-EU actors see EU market access as attractive but burdensome. Traceability and geolocation requirements pose particular challenges for SMEs and smallholders, who risk exclusion from EU markets. Normative (reputation) and cultural-cognitive (values) logics were found to play only a moderate role, varying with context. Overall, the regulation's effectiveness depends on strict enforcement, clear

communication, and economic support for smallholders to avoid exacerbating inequalities.

D5.2 emphasized the risks of spillover effects such as leakage, market segregation, and policy evasion (Table 1). Since EU market share is limited in many commodities, there is a danger that “clean” products are supplied to the EU while deforestation-linked goods are diverted elsewhere. These risks can significantly reduce global effectiveness, meaning the EUDR alone will not suffice and must be combined with complementary supply-side measures.

Table 1. EUDR potential spillover effects (from stakeholder interviews) discussed by D5.2.

Spillover effects	Potential spillover effects	Brazil (agriculture)	Brazil (forestry)	Camer-oon (forestry)	Gabon (forestry)
Leakage	Activity displacement	Supply base adaptation discussed as key strategy	Supply base adaptation discussed as key strategy	-	-
	Market displacement with larger deforestation impact	Increase deforestation in the North; these products are not for EU export	-	-	-
Evasion	Export to other countries	Mixed views on shift from EU market	Mixed views on shift from EU market	Shift out of EU markets is expected	Shift out of EU market is possible
	Export other commodities	Not predicted	Not predicted	Not predicted	Not predicted
	Shift to domestic market	-	-	-	Possible strategy of smaller companies
	Market segregation of exports	Expected but complex	Expected but complex, espec. for wood pulp	Mixed views	Not expected
Others	Inequalities	Due to streamlining supply chains and actors' exclusions	Due to streamlining supply chains and actors' exclusions	-	Small companies excluded from the EU market

*Boosting is excluded from the table because it was discussed only in the European interviews; – factor not mentioned.

D5.3 concluded that while the EUDR is a bold politically step toward addressing deforestation, it will mainly create clean EU supply chains rather than significantly reducing global deforestation unless similar measures are adopted in other major

markets. Leakage, smallholder exclusion, and potential trade frictions are key risks. The study stresses that demand-side regulations must be complemented by supply-side measures such as stronger monitoring, local capacity-building, and land tenure clarification to tackle root causes.

Taken together, CLEVER shows that the effectiveness of policy and governance initiatives depends on a combination of determinants:

- Trade structures and market coverage (sticky traders, market shares, demand-side preferences).
- Policy design and coherence across instruments and levels (synergies vs. competition among intervention logics).
- Behavioral responses of businesses, especially SMEs and smallholders, to compliance requirements.
- International coordination and burden-sharing between exporters and importers.

Evidence from this line of CLEVER research suggests that both exporters and importers benefit from trade in agricultural and forest commodities, while the environmental costs fall disproportionately on producer countries. As such, global environmental governance requires cooperation, including knowledge and technology transfer, investment in monitoring, and effective enforcement in producing regions.

In sum, CLEVER demonstrates that while governance initiatives like the EUDR and voluntary supply-chain interventions can yield important results, their overall effectiveness depends on interaction effects, international alignment, and the provision of incentives and capacities that allow producers and traders to comply without simply diverting risks elsewhere.

iii) Scenarios

Scenario analysis in CLEVER explored how different shared socioeconomic pathways (SSPs) for different supply chains and trade governance interventions may shape the impacts of non-food biomass trade on biodiversity, climate, and ecosystems. Results from WP6 and WP7 show that while certain pathways can reduce pressures, trade-related biodiversity risks are likely to persist unless global production and consumption systems shift towards more sustainable trajectories.

The case study on the Brazilian soy sector (D6.3) highlighted land stress (through both land transformation and land occupation) as the dominant driver of biodiversity loss. Scenario modelling showed that unless the world follows a sustainability pathway (SSP1), pressures on biodiversity will continue to rise, with soybean cropland expansion shifting across major Brazilian biomes. In SSP1, reduced land-use change leads to the largest decrease in biodiversity impacts, offering a pathway to mitigate future losses.

Complementary life-cycle assessment results (D6.4) emphasize that the biodiversity footprint of soy exports is strongly shaped by their municipality of origin (Figure 4), which determines the intensity of land occupation, land transformation, and input use. In particular, biodiversity risks correlate with deforestation only when land transformation dominates over occupation. Beyond biodiversity, the production of agricultural inputs, especially fertilizers, emerges as a major contributor to carbon emissions, water use, and health damages, underscoring the interdependencies between environmental and social dimensions.

Figure 4. Biodiversity footprint of soy commodities traded from different locations in Brazil to the EU, calculated at the D6.4.

Building on these findings, WP7 examined sectoral scenarios for the Brazilian soy trade (D7.2). Under a business-as-usual (BAU) scenario, Brazil's soy exports are projected to grow significantly, particularly to China, while the EU's market share continues to decline. Such growth does not necessarily lead to higher deforestation under current policies and may occur without expanding agricultural land. However, it is still likely to reduce biodiversity by converting low-intensity native grasslands.

By contrast, scenarios aiming to “bend the curve”, such as those involving dietary shifts reducing demand for soy-based products, result in much lower growth opportunities for Brazil, but also reduce biodiversity trade-offs. These contrasting trajectories create strong incentives for Brazilian actors to demonstrate the provision of “clean” soy to secure long-term market access.

Scenario analysis of governance measures (D7.3) shows that EU demand-side policies, including the EUDR and EUM, are expected to have only modest impacts on deforestation trends in Brazil if they do not significantly alter overall supply levels (Figure 5). Similarly, the potential spillover effects of other interventions, whether negative (e.g., absence of the Amazon Soy Moratorium) or positive (e.g., Zero Net Loss pledges), remain limited compared to the influence of structural drivers such as global demand, unless restoration commitments increase substantially.

Figure 5. Trends in biodiversity impact for terrestrial ecosystems according to different mixed-policies scenarios calculated in D7.3

This implies that EU policies on their own are unlikely to drive large-scale biodiversity benefits, especially in the absence of parallel measures in other major markets such as China. Without broader international coordination, there remains a significant risk of leakage, with deforestation-linked production diverted to less regulated markets.

Taken together, CLEVER's scenario work highlights that:

- Land-use dynamics are the critical determinant of biodiversity outcomes, with SSP1 sustainability pathways offering the most promising reductions in impacts.
- Spatial origin matters: municipalities and input intensity strongly influence biodiversity footprints.
- BAU trade growth may avoid deforestation but still erode biodiversity, particularly in grassland ecosystems.

- Demand-side regulations like the EUDR contribute, but have limited reach without broader market coverage and stronger restoration commitments.

iv) Policy recommendations

In recent years, the EU has advanced several legislative initiatives to reduce its global biodiversity footprint. Recognizing that biodiversity loss is increasingly “embedded” in EU imports, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 mandates the inclusion of biodiversity provisions in all Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) and stricter impact assessments of EU trade on ecosystems.

CLEVER evidence on the EUDR

A landmark step is the EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR), which requires that selected forest-risk commodities (cattle, cocoa, coffee, natural rubber, palm oil, soy, and timber) placed on the EU market are deforestation-free and traceable back to their place of origin. While this represents an important advance and a clear example of the Brussels effect, CLEVER research highlights significant gaps in scope and implementation that limit its effectiveness in reducing global forest loss.

Some of the gaps raised by the WP4-5 were:

- Limited EU market leverage. In many producer countries (e.g., Brazil, Cameroon), the EU holds a relatively small market share of forest-risk commodities. Unless other major importers such as China and the US adopt similar measures, the EUDR will have limited global effect.
- Risk of weakening domestic policies. In Brazil, inconsistencies between EUDR rules and the Amazon Soy Moratorium gave political opponents new arguments to renegotiate existing rules, thereby undermining a policy mix that had successfully reduced deforestation (research paper in Nature Ecology & Evolution).
- Supply chain segregation: Even with perfect implementation, the EUDR risks simply “cleaning up” EU supply chains (D5.3). Deforestation-linked commodities could still flow to non-EU markets, creating a two-tier system rather than global reductions.
- Spillovers and diffusion: While D5.2 stresses that the EUDR could set an example and influence other consumers via policy diffusion, this outcome depends on international cooperation and multilateral partnerships.

Producer countries' stakeholders' perspectives

In the Congo Basin, WP5 and WP8 collected perspectives from timber stakeholders in Cameroon and Gabon (October 2024). Four main themes emerged:

1. Uneven business readiness: Larger (often European-owned) companies with certification systems see the EUDR as manageable, while smaller local operators expect severe challenges and may shift exports to less regulated markets.
2. Reshaping supply chains: A “two-tier system” may emerge, where deforestation-free timber goes to the EU, while non-compliant timber is diverted to Asian or intra-African markets, limiting global forest benefits.
3. Barriers to compliance and enforcement: Traceability from harvest plot to final product is complex, especially for processed goods (e.g., wooden furniture). Risks of “commodity laundering” remain high.
4. Capacity needs: Stakeholders emphasized that with the right incentives and technical/financial support, both public and private actors could comply. EU engagement is essential to avoid marginalizing SMEs and to build monitoring and enforcement capacity in producer countries.

In Brazil, similar risks are observed in soy supply chains: while the EUDR aligns with forest-protection goals, incoherencies with domestic governance mechanisms (Amazon Soy Moratorium, Forest Code) can undermine existing strategies (WP4/D4.3). These findings underline the importance of partnerships, capacity-building, and alignment with existing producer countries' governance systems.

Beyond the EUDR, WP2 findings on the drivers of biodiversity loss in tropical regions also suggest that the Global Biodiversity Framework's “30 by 30” target (to protect 30% of land, water, and oceans by 2030) needs additional provisions to be effective. For example, setting targets at specific spatial scales would help to avoid that opportunistic behavior limits the effectiveness of national efforts to comply with the global target. Stronger definitions, monitoring, and cooperation are key to making sure both global commitments and EU policies truly protect nature.

Across its analyses, CLEVER identifies three broader lessons:

- Policy coherence (WP4, WP5): The EUDR interacts with producer-country policies in ways that can be coordinated but also competitive. EU policies must avoid undermining results from national initiatives, and ensure alignment with other trade agreements (e.g., EU-Mercosur FTA).
- Financial sector role: Current regulations insufficiently address the biodiversity impacts of the financial sector. Mandatory biodiversity risk disclosure and redirection of harmful subsidies are needed.
- Partnerships and co-design (WP8, D8.7): Participatory governance and co-created solutions with producers, SMEs, and civil society are essential. Without them, compliance risks reinforcing inequalities and fueling resistance. The

catalogue of narratives (D8.7) stresses that alternative tools, such as deforestation-linked commodity taxes, with revenues reinvested in producer countries, could complement regulations while supporting restoration.

09 Priorities for EU policymakers

The evidence found during the CLEVER project points to several priorities for EU policymakers. These results can also be directly used by science–policy platforms such as IPBES, IPCC, CBD, and Bio-Agora, helping to translate evidence into actionable global governance. The priorities for the EU to reduce its biodiversity impacts from trade are:

- Expand scope: Broaden coverage beyond forest ecosystems to include other threatened ecosystems (e.g., savannas, grasslands) and avoid deforestation leakage (*source: upcoming Cluster policy brief*).
- Ensure coherence: Align EU trade, agriculture, energy, and infrastructure policies with biodiversity goals. Prevent provisions in FTAs (e.g., EU-Mercosur) from undermining EUDR objectives (*source: upcoming Cluster policy brief, D4.3*).
- Strengthen enforcement: Guarantee strict and even enforcement within the EU to avoid laundering of non-compliant products (*source: D5.1*).
- Support producer countries: Provide targeted technical and financial assistance for SMEs and local governments to meet compliance requirements and strengthen enforcement capacities (*source: D5.3*).
- Engage finance: Introduce mandatory biodiversity risk disclosure in EU financial regulation, redirect subsidies, and ensure EU investments support nature-positive outcomes (*source: upcoming Cluster policy brief*).
- Prevent leakage and segregation: Work with major consumer countries (China, US) to adopt similar due diligence measures, reducing risks of deforestation leakage and market segregation (*source: D5.2, D5.3*).
- Complement demand-side with supply-side measures: Invest in monitoring, land tenure security, and restoration in producer countries, ensuring regulations address root causes of deforestation (*source: D5.3*).
- Maintain focus on well-established conservation policies: Ensure that EUDR and private policies do not divert attention from protected areas, payments for ecosystem services, and other conservation tools (*source: D8.7, upcoming Cluster policy brief*).
- Strengthen co-design: Institutionalize transparent stakeholder engagement in EU policy planning to ensure inclusive, just, and effective outcomes (*source: D8.7, upcoming Cluster policy brief*).

